

Myth: AI is disrupting knowledge work

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Recently, applications based on machine learning have made enormous progress and can now take over tasks such as translations, document search or image recognition. Now, many fear that knowledge work will fundamentally change and eventually many knowledge workers will lose their jobs.

Myth

AI is disrupting knowledge work.

Indeed, companies are using AI applications to automate or augment very specific parts of knowledge work. However, new tasks are created in the process and the tasks that can be automated are usually very modular and delimited. Knowledge work relates to tasks in which knowledge, rather than services or physical goods, must be developed and deployed at the core.

Materials

Folien der Präsentation

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UNICORN IN THE FIELD

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Why, AI?

This post is part of our project “Why, AI?”. It is a learning space which helps you to find out more about the myths and truths surrounding automation, algorithms, society and ourselves. It is continuously being filled with new contributions.

[Explore all myths](#)
